

FIDAL Beyond 5G: trials overview, current challenges and expected outcomes

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Abstract—Evolved 5G communication is disrupting the regular mobile broadband communication compared to previous generations by providing ultra-high speed, ultra-low latency, and allowing ultra-multi connections with low power consumptions, paving the way to a reality where physical and digital world are interconnected. Project FIDAL aims to explore and demonstrate Beyond 5G technologies through large-scale trials and pilots with the aim to promote architectures that allow multiple experimentation sites with a multi-stakeholder approach in PPDR and Media. In this paper, the project is presenting examples of current challenges, results and expected outcomes from two of its testbed sites: Univeristy of Patras and Telenor.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of mobile communications systems has become extremely fast. It is reported [1] that by the end of 2022 there were about 1B 5G subscriptions with a forecast of over 5B in 2028, with an average data consumption of more than 19GB per month, from which, 80% is expected to be video traffic. The expansion of 5G mobile communications was faster than the previous generations and is expected to provide ultra-high speed and ultra-low latency while allowing ultra-multi connections with low power consumption, enhancing many vertical industries. Beyond 5G technologies aims to further enhance the support of services provided by these technologies. Evolved 5G and 6G research requires the preparation and deployment of multiple possible ideas from which the most mature and fitting can be moved to standardization or into innovation activities of industry forums and individual companies. To share the financial burden and facilitate a discussion among interested parties which can come to an agreement on the most promising research areas, collaborative research and innovation is crucial.

Advances in digital technology allow the physical world to come together with its digital counterpart in the form of Digital Twins (DT) which enable the study of a physical system in a controlled digital environment. These DT are virtual representations of the real-life situation continuously updated in real time by the actual events in the physical system allowing for better prediction and decision-making processes for the real-life counterparts. Digital services that combine physical elements with virtual reality experience can emerge by integrating the advanced capabilities of emerging technologies allowing linking of human senses with remote data, thus paving the way for haptic applications.

Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) and Media are verticals that require different support levels for converting

concepts to prototypes, hence the need for further research and development which will take advantage of the above-mentioned technological advances.

The authors of this paper are involved in FIDAL, a Horizon Europe Project under stream D of the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU). The projects aims to explore and demonstrate Beyond 5G technologies by implementing large-scale trials and pilots with aim to promote architectures that allow multiple experimentation sites with a multi-stakeholder approach in the PPDR and Media areas. The ultimate goal is to support these verticals by stretching the respective Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) [2] of the use cases on the way to Beyond 5G by understanding the needs and advancing the solution performance and KPIs.

The approach to the initial testing and validation of the use cases is presented along with the tests results of one of the involved testbeds.

II. FIDAL PROJECT

FIDAL plans to prepare the way for Beyond 5G and 6G networks by combining the experiences and lessons learned from the various ICT-41 projects of different vertical domains into a unified collaboration with network application development, deployment and life cycle management, in a cross-industry oriented collaboration while adding and enhancing aspects like Security and Zero Touch Management. FIDAL's main goal is the creation and deployment of a testing framework which will help validation of beyond 5G technologies in preparation for 6G. The overall block diagram architecture and FIDAL infrastructure is illustrated in Figure 1

A. Network Applications

FIDAL's ambition is to stretch the respective Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) [2] of the use cases on the way to 5G beyond. FIDAL aims to address security and integration challenges for the Network Applications that will be deployed, taking into consideration both the requirements of the vertical that is supported and the possible placement requirements, while developing DevOps driven approaches for their deployment. Network Applications will be supported with minimum downtime while incorporating AIasS and SaaS.

B. Orchestration

FIDAL aims to address the drawbacks of existing orchestration solutions by advancing the orchestration approach by

Fig. 1. FIDAL Architecture and Infrastructure

deploying an orchestrator able to manage and deploy tasks across various sites of differing architectures and functionalities. The end goal is the design of a distributed orchestration mechanism that will decrease service time provisioning.

C. Zero Touch Management

FIDAL aims to use the Deep Reinforcement Learning DRL approach from the MonB5G European project [3] and enhance it to address issues that are related to mission critical areas. A novel DRL architecture will be deployed solving the conflicts that arise from the distributed RL agents deployed in the various network elements. In this way only local reconfiguration will be required affecting part of the network flow.

D. AI Tools

FIDAL aims to develop tools based on Auto Machine Learning (AutoML) while deploying models adapted to the specific nature of Media and PPDR verticals. To avoid the generality classic ML for cross-domain applications, a series of services will be generated in the form of AaaS offering capabilities for the generation of self adaptive ML models with specific orientation to each vertical. These models will also be able to detect changes in the network requirements during the vertical's own operation. These new predictive models will self-adapt accordingly, leading to an on-the-fly replacement of the model.

E. Security

FIDAL's ambition is to make sure that a secure system is in place for the future of 5G and 6G technology. This system will include structures, processes, technologies, enablers, vendors, and service providers incorporating AI/ML elements across 6G security architecture, process and technology domains.

III. TRIALS IN FIDAL

As mentioned before, FIDAL aims to deploy, test and validate a number of use cases in the Media and PPDR verticals. The internal cases can be seen in table I while more use cases will be developed through Open Calls that will make FIDAL infrastructure available to the public.

These tests will be executed in the participating laboratories (UMA, pNet-UoP and TNOR) and then demonstrated in large-scale trials.

Media Vertical	
Use Case	Lab
Internet of Senses/Haptic sensing	UMA
Advanced sports area media services	UoP, PNET
Virtual Reality Networked music performance	TNOR
Smart village engagement services	TNOR
PPDR Vertical	
Digital Twin for first responders	UoP, PNET
City security event / incident	UMA
XR-assisted services for public safety	UoP, PNET

TABLE I. USE CASES

A. Dry runs

For the execution of the dry run tests, the experimentation methodology defined in the 5GENESIS [4] project was adopted. The 5GENESIS project's experimentation methodology provides a comprehensive and rigorous approach to evaluate the performance of the testbeds and trials that will be involved in the demonstration of the use cases covered by the project.

The test cases are structured around three concepts:

- the test cases, which define the target of the experiment, the procedure, and the measurements that must be collected to validate the targeted KPIs.
- the experimentation scenarios, which detail the end-to-end conditions for running the experiments, such as the network configuration and the mobility conditions of the User Equipment (UE).
- Background traffic conditions

B. Lab verification

Lab validation of all UCs will be performed in three testbeds deployed in previous European projects. Advanced 5G functionalities, such as 5G NR and extreme coverage in the testbeds will be performed. FIDAL will introduce a logical separation between experimentation facility development taking place within the testbeds themselves for the addition of new or updated Network Applications and their associated VNFs. All Network Applications must first be tested and validated (i.e., qualified) before being considered suitable for addition to the Network Applications Repository (e.g., whether they meet the KPI requirements). The testbeds will be updated in collaboration with the technology vendors to ensure 5G evolution lab validations.

C. Large Scale

FIDAL will validate 5G evolution enabling technologies' features and capabilities in real-life scenarios as well as in each UC to be tested. Such large-scale trials will be supported by 5G evolution infrastructure as well as the FIDAL framework that will be deployed in collaboration with the technology vendors thus being able to validate the technology in near commercial conditions. Security processes will be strictly designed, adopted, and audited to ensure that commercial infrastructures will not be impacted by the deployment and operation of the test facilities.

IV. RESULTS

Description of the trials results per lab

A. UoP Results

The initial steps involved conducting dry runs, which required the execution of a series of predefined common test cases. These tests were designed to evaluate and benchmark the critical Key Performance Indicators of the laboratories before validating them for any of the corresponding use case.

1) *UoP Results - DRY RUN*: To verify the laboratory's capabilities at the University of Patras (UoP), as detailed in the Patras 5G Wiki [5], the setup depicted in Figure 2 was deployed, and the necessary tests were conducted. These tests included performance, latency, and reliability metrics, as outlined in the previous section. During the testing phase, communication between the client and server occurred over the 5G network. Given that the client was a Virtual Machine (VM) lacking 5G capability, a Customer Premises Equipment (CPE) was used. This CPE served as a 5G gateway, facilitating access to the 5G network.

Following the tests, the results were collected and processed for analysis.

Fig. 2. Dry Run Setup for UoP/pNet and TNOR lab. Image courtesy of UoP

The initial measured results for the performance test can be seen in table II and will serve as the baseline for the next round of tests. These are the mean values gathered over 25 repetitions of the performance test.

iPerf Measured Results (Mean Value) (Mbps)				
	Stream Direction	Downlink Configuration	Uplink Configuration	
TCP	Downstream	429.31	141.65	
TCP	Upstream	68	256.77	
UDL	Downstream	688.91	80.25	
UDL	Upstream	62.62	254.67	

TABLE II. INITIAL PERFORMANCE RESULTS

2) *UoP Results - LAB VALIDATION*: In figure 3, the setup used for the validation tests in pNet/UoP laboratory can be seen. The basic setup for each experiment was the deployment of a 5G network. This ensured the connectivity between the devices used in the experiments and the corresponding Network Applications. Depending on the Network Application and the experiment requirements, GPU access was also provided per case.

To access the network, various UEs were used, like 5G-enabled mobile phones. For cases where the end-user device was not 5G ready, a CPE was used as a gateway by providing 5G back-haul access and allowing legacy devices to connect, either through Ethernet or WiFi.

The 5G core network deployed can be configured to satisfy various requirements of the 5G tested scenarios. By modifying the configuration parameters, the deployed network can be oriented in downlink configuration. This means that more resources are allocated for the downlink path (gNB to UE), and therefore the downlink bandwidth of the network can be maximised. If the experiment requires the UE to send data as fast as possible (via the uplink), the correct configuration can be applied to satisfy this, as well. Finally, a low latency configuration is also available, if required depending on the configuration of the 5G network.

Fig. 3. Validation test setup for UoP/pNet lab
An overview of the use cases tested can be seen in Table III.

a) *Advanced sports area media services*: A media-related use case where a number of UEs would stream to the network application. The configuration used was aimed at maximising upload speeds. 5G capable mobile phones which had the appropriate mobile application installed were used.

b) *Digital Twin for first responders*: This is a PPDR related Use Case. During the validation tests cameras were

used to stream video to the deployed network application. Since the device was not 5G ready a CPE was used. The setup was oriented for maximising upload speed.

c) *XR-assisted services for public safety* : This UC consists of two use cases. Both use cases include Head Mounted Units (HMU) for VR/AR purposes. One UC is mainly focusing on downstream while the other is upstream oriented. Each use case was tested separately, where the configuration was set on the intended target for each use case.

Use Cases tested during validation tests		
UC name	Protocol	Traffic Direction
Advanced sports area media services	RTP	UL
Digital Twin for first responders	RTP	UL
XR-assisted services for public safety UC1	UDP	DL
XR-assisted services for public safety UC2	TCP/RTP	UL

TABLE III. PERFORMED EXPERIMENTS

B. TNOR Results

TNOR’s large-scale experimentation platform, i-CORA [6], will support both the lab validation and large-scale trials of FIDAL Media use cases.

1) *TNOR Results - DRY RUN*: Dry run tests have been performed for initial assessment of the testbed performance. The test setup is similar to Figure 2, but using a laptop as client. Throughput, latency and reliability have been tested using iPerf. For instance, the throughput results are indicated in table IV

iPerf Measured Results (Mean Value)		
	Downlink Throughput	Uplink Throughput
TCP	801.1 Mbps	104.8 Mbps
UDP	873.1 Mbps	106.1 Mbps

TABLE IV. TNOR TESTBED INITIAL PERFORMANCE RESULTS

2) *TNOR Results - LAB VALIDATION*: In terms of the Virtual Reality Networked Music Performance use case (UC5), the initial versions of the Network Application, smartphone application and video player have been validated in the testbed. Figure 4 illustrates the validation setup, in which two radio sites are needed for the musician locations. The radio sites are both connected to the 5G SA core, and finally, the Network Application. In each musician location, a 5G smartphone is capturing the video, while two laptops are used for: (i) audio processing; and (ii) video streaming from the other musician.

Fig. 4. TNOR lab test setup

V. CONCLUSION

In this work we present the first promising results of the validation tests of the demanding use cases to be tested during

the FIDAL project life-cycle. These results will be used as feedback to further enhance the use cases and prepare for the large scale trials of these.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work of the authors has been partially supported by the Horizon Europe Project FIDAL (grant agreement No. 101096146).

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